

THE IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Ismatova Mekhribon¹

4- year student of
Supervisor

Ulasheva Shakhlo²

Technologies named after Muhammad
al-Khwarizmi Karshi branch

¹⁻²Tashkent University of Information

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Abstract: This article talks about the importance of innovative technologies in learning foreign languages. The author, relying on scientific data, analyzed the problem on the basis of existing literature, studied the specific aspects of the importance of innovative technologies in learning foreign languages.

Keywords: English language, innovative technology, media, internet, international.

In the current era of globalization, researching innovative educational technologies and their pedagogical foundations, researching ways to effectively use modern interactive teaching methods in the educational process remains one of the urgent problems of today.

The socio-pedagogical necessity of an innovative approach to education is measured by:

1. Scientific-technical development and socio-economic renewal of the continuous education system, in particular, improvement of the educational process in educational institutions using the study of advanced foreign experiences, innovative approaches in education and information technologies;
2. Creation and implementation of effective organizational forms and technologies of person-oriented education that serve to develop the level of education, intellectual potential, social activity, and creativity skills of students;
3. The need to develop the professional-innovative competence of the teacher in relation to mastering and implementing pedagogical innovations.

After our country gained independence, the demand and interest in learning foreign languages increased. Many opportunities have been created for students. Effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process and the introduction of modern innovative technologies into the educational process improve the quality and efficiency of education. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. Innovative technologies are very important in language learning and teaching. The use of

technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, writing, listening, speaking). For example, in order to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, CD discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the reader is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings.

☒ An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know and use information and communication technologies well. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, including:

☒ when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language;

☒ foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs can be heard and watched;

☒ use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method;

☒ CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of learning a foreign language more interesting and effective for students [1].

It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their capabilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger.

The use of game technology relies on the student's fundamental needs for self-expression, finding a stable place in life, self-management, and realizing one's potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects.

In the process of games, the student is more interested in this activity than in a regular lesson and works freely. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching. Pupils participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher also provides education to the pupil through them. The student believes and is interested in playing English games, speaking, listening, and writing [2].

In the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes

is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues from the United States of America and England:

☒ To use this method of "Creative Problem Solving", the beginning of the story is read and the end of the story is referred to the judgment of the students;

☒ "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to riddles;

☒ "Quick answers" helps to improve the effectiveness of the lesson;

☒ "Chigil yozdi" ("Warm-up exercises") use various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson [3];

☒ "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are done and students are tired;

☒ The method of "a chain story" helps to develop oral speech of students;

☒ "Role games" (Acting characters), this method can be used in all types of lessons;

☒ "Thinkers meeting" poets and writers can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people;

☒ The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop students' oral speech;

☒ Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time [4].

Technical means to improve the quality of education: audio-video, film materials, computers, video projector, slides, excerpts from works of art; they use modern pedagogical technologies, especially interactive methods.

Innovative educational technologies improve the quality of education, increase its effectiveness, establish mutual cooperation between the teacher, student and the team, achieve ideological and spiritual unity, strive for a single goal, each It has great potential in creating the necessary conditions and environment for the realization of the learner's inner potential, manifestation as a person.

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical and critical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to quickly and correctly answer is formed. Such methods make

the student eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process.

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